

Self-healing of Structural Damage in Thermoplastic Composite Laminates via Incorporated Nano-engineered Heating Architecture

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Existing Repairing Mechanisms of Composites

- In-situ inspection and direct addition of composite material into the damaged region is currently utilized
- Repair techniques and researches of thermoset resin matrix composites are more common

<Scarfing Repair Techniques^[1]>

<Injection Repair Technique^[2]>

<Doubler Patch Repair^[3]>

Why Thermoplastics? Reversibility and Crystallization

- Thermoplastic polymer matrices soften and melt when heated and solidifies **reversibly** when cooled
- During the cooling phase, the thermoplastic matrix undergoes **crystallization**
- The **slower the cooling rate**, more crystallization occurs, leading to **higher mechanical properties**
- With its reversibility and crystallizing properties, the thermoplastic composite with damaged crack can be “**self-healed**” by filling the crack with liquefied matrix during the temperature cycle

<Crystalline and amorphous regions of a polymer^[1]>

<Degree of crystallinity (DOC) decreases with faster cooling rates^[2]>

Current Self-healing: Healing Agent Capsules

- With the reversible phase changeability of thermoplastic matrices, currently used self-healing techniques involve healing agents capsuled into the composite structures
- When the crack is formed, the healing agent ruptures and fills the crack during the curing process
- However, the major setback of this method is the **lack of repeatability**, therefore the implementation of the **repeatable heating nano-architecture via Joule heating** onto the thermoplastic composite is utilized as a solution in this research

<Thermoset matrix composites with thermoplastic particles for self-healing^[1]>

<Self-healing via encapsulated healing agents>

Carbon Nanotube (CNT) Heater as a Nano-engineered Heating Architecture

- The Carbon Nanotube (CNT) heater nano-architecture uses Joule heating
- Existing research shows the CNT heater being able to heat towards 400°C and above
- The CNT heater can be performed repeatedly in a desired amount of time and number of cycles
- Therefore the CNT heater is used as a main structure of **self-healing nano-architecture** for this research

<The heating performance of CNT Heater Nano-architecture^[1]>

<The repeatability of the CNT heater performance^[2]>

Further Research Required for the Self-healing Architecture

⊖ Sustainable self-healing structure and method throughout the entire temperature cycle

- Self-healing cycle based on manufacturer's instructions
- The nanoarchitecture must be free of electrical shorts via sufficient electrical insulation

⊖ Consistent mechanical test methods for self-healed composites testing

- Finding the appropriate mechanical test for thermoplastic matrix based composites
- Sufficient amount of test data for such materials is required for further self-healing research

Matrix damage (Crack)

Matrix melting by heat (Self-healing)

Healed damage

<Schematic of the Self-healing process>

Research Objectives

- 1) **Incorporating the CNT heater-based nano-engineered heating architecture to the thermoplastic composite (PA6)**
 - Targeting on structurally incorporated nanocomposite integration

- 2) **Short Beam Shear (SBS) and End-Notched Flexural (ENF) Testing of nanocomposite-integrated structure for self-healing efficacy**
 - Stiffness analysis via the SBS test
 - Mode II Toughness analysis via the ENF test

- 3) **Morphological analogy of the self-healing effects on the nanocomposites**
 - Visual effects of the CNT-heater self-healing via the optical microscope
 - Visual analysis of the mechanical test specimens

The Surface Incorporation of the Heater Architecture for the Thermoplastic Composites

- **Carbon fiber (CF) / Polyamide 6 (PA6)** prepreg by SHINDO, Japan was chosen as composite material
- The **nano-engineered heating architecture (CNT heater)** is composed by the **Carbon Nanotube (CNT)** bucky paper and the **copper electrode**, joined together by **silver epoxy**
- As Carbon fiber is electrically conductive, extra PA6 films were layered for **electrical insulation**
- **Vacuum-bag-only (VBO)** method was used to prevent PA6 from discoloring throughout the curing process

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The Effectiveness of the CNT Heater is Realized and Utilized in this Research

<CNT heater implemented on the composite sample>

<IR Recording of the CNT Heater>

- CNT heater is used for self-healing of the thermoplastic matrix composites
- Design of implementation of CNT heater into the composites is the scope of this research

Short Beam Shear Testing (SBS) for Self-Healing Effects on the Stiffness

<SBS Test Setup Design^[1] (Left) & Actual Photo (Right)>

"Baseline" 0° UD 48 layers	"Infusion" (CNT + PA6 infusion layer) 0° UD 48 layers	"Pre-cracked" (with film insert) 0° UD 48 layers	"Self-healed" (via CNT heater) 0° UD 48 layers

- The main objective of the SBS test (**ASTM D2344**) is to obtain the short beam strength, however due to the ductile properties of the PA6 matrix, the bending stiffness was calculated instead

End-Notched Flexural Testing (ENF) for Self-Healing Effects on the Mode II Toughness

<ENF Test Setup Design(Left)^[1] & Actual Photo(Right)>

- The main objective of the ENF test (**ASTM D7905**) is to obtain the Mode II toughness values of the specimen via Compliance Calibration method (CC)
- The film insert with release agent treatment was used to create the pre-crack for both SBS and ENF specimens 13

End-Notched Flexural Testing (ENF) for Self-Healing Effects on the Mode II Toughness

- The ENF test consists of an **NPC** and a **PC** test, and both tests require **two Compliance Calibration (CC) tests** and a **fracture test**
- The NPC test aims to observe the toughness based on a **film insert pre-crack**, while the PC test is based on a **propagated crack**
- The CC tests and a fracture test yield the load-displacement curves to analyze the **compliance values** with respect to the adjusted pre-crack length

<Side view of the ENF test>

Manufacturing the Specimens for Mechanical Testing

- All specimens with specific conditions for each sample groups were stacked and oven-cured, then prepared in final desired dimensions for each mechanical tests

Self-healing the Specimens for Mechanical Testing

SBS Test

ENF Test

- For both SBS and ENF test specimens, self-healing was performed in a vacuum condition via the **VBO method**
- The **Aluminum mold**, customized according to specimen dimensions, was used to contain and preserve the geometry of the specimen
- **Alumina-Silicate boards** were used as **thermal insulators** to minimize the heat loss
- **Thermocouples** were used over IR camera due to the heat insulation of the ceramic board

Matching the Self-healing Cycle with the Oven Curing

- For all self-healing procedures, the self-healing temperature cycle followed the original oven curing cycle for making the composite sample specimens
- The self-healing cycle was controlled to match the oven cycle in order to remove the possible effects of difference in crystallinity on the mechanical properties

Morphological Analysis of SBS Specimen

- Visible crack by the film insert (“Pre-cracked”) is completely reconsolidated in the self-healed specimen (“Self-healed”)
- Both specimens are separate samples, therefore the void content showed differences between different sample groups

Recovery of the Normalized Stiffness by Self-healing

- **Maximum derivative value** of the **initial load-increasing region** is represented as the bending stiffness
- The calculated bending stiffness is normalized by the **second moment of area**
- The **“Self-healed” specimen** achieved the **same level of normalized stiffness** as the **ucky paper-PA6 “Infusion” specimen**, meaning self-healing was successful

The Addition of Bucky Paper-PA6 Infusion Layer Lowers the Total Normalized Stiffness

<“Baseline”>

<“Infusion”>

- “Infusion” specimen resembles a **sandwich-structured composite** panel material, with the bucky paper-PA6 infusion layer as the outer skin and the “Baseline” prepreg layer in between
- The normalized stiffness ratio of the “Infusion” to the “Baseline” **experimentally** turned out to be **0.7886**, while the **theoretical ratio** based on parameters obtained through morphology turned out to be **0.61638**

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Crack Propagation of ENF Specimen

- (a1) “Baseline”, initial state
- (a2) “Baseline”, after ENF test
- (b1) “Heater-attached”, initial state
- (b2) “Heater-attached”, after ENF test
- (b3) “Heater-healed”, initial state
- (b4) “Heater-healed”, after ENF test
- In terms of crack length, (b3) was recovered to that of (b1)

Mode II Toughness Comparison Results of ENF Specimen

Sample Group	A	B(before self-healing)	B(after self-healing)
$G_{IIc}(NPC)$	1.7882 ± 0.1463	2.0095 ± 0.1036	1.9494 ± 0.2094
$G_{IIc}(PC)$	1.9494 ± 0.2094	2.0946 ± 0.1006	2.4373 ± 0.7253

- **97% recovery of Mode II toughness** was shown in **“Heater-healed”** compared to **“Heater-attached”** (NPC)
- **“Heater-attached”** showed higher toughness than the **“Baseline”**
- **“Heater-healed”** showed higher toughness with higher SD, due to **different crack propagations** after the NPC test
- More data with consistent specimen form preservation will be obtained in the future

Conclusion

- 1) Morphology presents the self-healing is successful for both SBS and ENF specimen
 - Pre-crack (SBS) and propagated crack (ENF) shown reconsolidation
- 2) Short Beam Shear (SBS) specimens showed normalized stiffness recovery compared to the specimen without the original pre-crack
 - The self-healing effect on the pre-crack is shown to be able to show full recovery
- 3) End-Notched Flexural (ENF) specimens showed around 90% mode II toughness recovery after self-healing compared to before self-healing
 - The NPC tests showed less deviations than the PC tests for the self-healed specimen
 - More form-preserved specimen data required

Future Work

Finding the temperature cycle for 100% self-healing efficiency

- Increasing the holding time or the cooling phase
- Adjusting the other temperature cycle parameters

Crystallinity analysis of existing samples with DSC

→ Cure cycle vs. Crystallinity

- Cooling time
- Holding time

→ Designing the most efficient self-healing cycle based on sample crystallinity

Manufacturing and self-healing the sample based on the designed self-healing cycle

- Crystallinity analysis
- Short Beam Shear testing

Compare the mechanical properties and the morphology between the self-healed specimen and non-self-healed

→ Attain 100% self-healing

Thank you for your attention

End-Notched Flexural Testing (ENF) for Self-Healing Effects on the Mode II Toughness

<Calculating the Compliances from the Load-Displacement Curve>

$$P_{c_{a_0}} (a_0 = 20\text{mm}, 40\text{mm}) = \frac{4B}{3a_0} \sqrt{G_{IIc} E_{11} h^3} a_0^3$$

<Calculating the slope of the Compliance-Crack length (a_0) linear fit>

$$G_Q = \frac{3mP_{max}^2 a_0^2}{2B} \quad (a_0 = 30\text{mm}, \text{Fracture Test})$$

$$\text{If } 0.15 \leq \left(\frac{P_{c_{a_i}} a_i}{P_{max} a_0} \right)^2 \leq 0.35 \quad (a_i = 20\text{mm}, 40\text{mm}),$$

$$G_Q = G_{IIc}$$

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Manufacturing the Specimens for Mechanical Testing

SBS Test

ENF Test

- For “Self-healed” SBS specimen, 40mmX40mm CNT bucky paper was used to make the heater
- For “Heater-attached” and “Heater-healed” ENF specimen, 50mmX180mm CNT bucky paper was used
- The stacking sequence in 3D expression is color coded as: Bright yellow(Film insert), Dark grey(Prepreg), Black(Bucky paper), Skyblue(Nylon film), Dark orange(PI film for cover), Bright orange(Copper electrode), Cylinders(Molds)

Manufacturing the Specimens for Mechanical Testing

SBS Test

ENF Test

Self-healing the Specimens for Mechanical Testing

ENF Test(Double-sample method)

ENF Test(Spacer method)

Load-Displacement Curves of the SBS Test

- Maximum derivative value of the initial load-increasing region is selected to represent the bending stiffness
- The calculated bending stiffness is normalized by the second moment of area

Stiffness Comparison Results of SBS Specimen

- Maximum derivative value of the initial load-increasing region is selected to represent the bending stiffness
- The calculated bending stiffness is normalized by the second moment of area

The Presence of the Crack Decreases the Mechanical Properties

< Decreasing Effective Young's modulus with increasing crack density^[1]>

<Cross-section of Pre-cracked specimen>

- Y Huang et al. showed that the **presence of micro-cracks**, such as in this research, possess a **decreasing effect** in the **total effective modulus** value
- $c = 0.0$ on the curve indicates zero inclusions, meaning zero spherical microparticles with different Young's modulus values
- Morphology of this experiment(specimen C) showed crack density = 0.00652, which approximately matches 0.9 on the curve
- Experimental data shows the stiffness ratio of pre-cracked(C) and without crack specimen(B) is 0.835

Preparation Procedure of ENF Specimen

- Baseline specimens showed uniform geometry as a baseline control group (a)
- Heater-attached specimens B2, B3, B5 in (b) showed deformations after self-healing (c1)
- All Heater-healed specimens were trimmed into a parallel rectangular shape for the ENF testing (c2)

Mode II Toughness Comparison Results of ENF Specimen: Experiment vs. Theory

$$G_{II} = \frac{9CP^2a^2}{2b(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \text{ (Theory, [1])}$$

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{3mP^2a^2}{2b} \text{ (ASTM D7905)}$$

$$\frac{\text{Experiment}}{\text{Theory}} = \frac{m}{\frac{3C}{2L^3 + 3a^3}}$$